

DEVELOPMENT OF LIVESTOCK INDUSTRY IN THE COUNTRY AS A COMPETITIVE INDUSTRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10980250>

Abstract. In this article, livestock production is being carried out on the country level, livestock production is being carried out on the roads of the livestock production and production of our modified products. An analysis of the usefulness of the livestock products produced by the production, as well as making proposals for the introduction of electronic technologies in the country in this field.

Key words: agriculture, livestock, digital technologies, statistics committee, farms, farmers and homesteads, organizations implementing agricultural activities.

Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada mamlakat miqyosida chorvachilik sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan o'zgarishlar, davlatimiz tomonidan berilayotgan imkoniyatlar, chorva mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarishni takomillashtirish yo'llarida taklif va mulohazalar berilgan. Ishlab chiqargan chorvachilik mahsulotlarining hududlar bo'yicha tahlili keltirilgan, bundan tashqari mamlakatda bu soha miqyosida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha takliflar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: chorvachilik, qishloq xo'jaligi, chorva mollari, raqamli texnologiyalar, statistika qo'mitasi, fermer xo'jaliklari, dehqon va tomorqa xo'jaliklari, qishloq xo'jaligi faoliyatini amalga oshiruvchi tashkilotlar.

Аннотация. В данной статье приведены изменения, реализуемые в сфере животноводства на уровне страны, возможности, предоставляемые нашим государством, предложения и комментарии по путям совершенствования производства продукции животноводства. Представлен анализ производимой продукции животноводства по регионам, а также представлены предложения по внедрению цифровых технологий в этой сфере в стране.

Ключевые слова: животноводство, сельское хозяйство, животноводство, цифровые технологии, комитет по статистике, фермы, фермерские и приусадебные хозяйства, организации, осуществляющие сельскохозяйственную деятельность.

Introduction

Digital technologies and the digital economy have entered so rapidly that today it is impossible to imagine not only our daily life, but also the development of social and economic spheres without them. Modern technologies and digitalization allow producers of livestock products to optimize their activities. The role of digital technologies, which serve to create effective production systems and reduce environmental impact, optimize production costs and increase efficiency, is significantly reflected day by day.

In the era of digital technologies, the issue of expanding the production of livestock products, which plays an important role in ensuring the well-being of the population, and developing its consumption among the population on a large scale, as well as supporting the reforms carried out in the field, is one of the strategic directions of the state policy. Filling with theoretical and practical materials and analysis of important, topical issues such as increasing the role of digital technologies in the production and consumption of livestock products in the region,

strengthening the welfare of the population, which is the social basis of our developing country, and filling the consumption basket We conducted research under the conditions of doing.

In order to support the work carried out in the field of animal husbandry in our country, instructions were given on the establishment of livestock clusters in 25 districts, state support for milk-producing and processing enterprises.¹ The President's Decision No. PQ-120 of February 8, 2022 "On approving the program for the development of the livestock sector and its branches in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" was approved.² The program is aimed at ensuring food security in the country by further increasing the production of livestock products, wide introduction of modern methods of production, development of cooperative relations, and state support of the livestock sector.

It is worth noting that the support of any large and small industry operating in the country's economy with regulatory documents, as well as decisions, decrees and orders that play an important role in the development of this industry, guarantee the development of the industry. Also, the "Roadmap" for the implementation of the tasks defined in the program for 2022-2026 on the development of the livestock industry and its industries in the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved. All of the above regulatory documents are the reason for the non-stop work of the industry at the national level and the establishment of modern ways of production of livestock products, ensuring the well-being of the population.

Export performance

Philip K. Thornton (2010) argues that historically, the use of traditional methods of animal husbandry and the increase in livestock productivity observed in recent decades are evident. At the same time, there have been significant changes in the composition of livestock products. If past changes in the demand for livestock products were met by a combination of traditional methods such as replacement, cross-breeding and in-breed selection, future changes will be more likely to be met by new techniques. After analyzing the decade and then giving the results, it means that the current era of digital technologies confirms these thoughts.

Mozammel Hoque (2022) acknowledges that livestock remains one of the world's most important sectors related to the economy, food security, and people's livelihoods. Animal husbandry is an important global industry that contributes significantly to the country's economy. It ensures food security and livelihoods for the majority of the world's population. By 2050, the global demand for livestock products is expected to double, mainly due to the development of the world's standard of living.

Sh. Suvankulov (2020) in the book "Mechanization and automation of animal husbandry" considers animal husbandry to be an important branch of agriculture, which provides valuable food products for the population, such as milk, meat, eggs, and leather, wool, and other raw materials for light industry. He described that it serves for the delivery of goods. The production of livestock products with its organizational and structural features differs sharply from the processes of production of agricultural products and is distinguished by its uniqueness. He is one of the scientists who studied the ways of automating the production of livestock products. This research is showing its results to this day.

¹ <https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/6849>

² <https://lex.uz/docs/-5858728>

Sh. K. Amirov (2023) gave an analysis of the production of livestock products on the national scale and developed ways to further increase the livestock feed base based on the Chinese experience.

V.V. Kirsanov (2023) Basics of livestock production technology are shown. Designs of devices, machines and equipment for complex mechanization of production processes are described. The rules of machinery and equipment operation systems and the basics of technological design of farms and complexes are considered.

F. Schneider and S. Tarawali (2021) Reflections on Sustainable Development Goals and Livestock Systems. In his research, the scientist proved that the livestock sector is a sector that can directly affect other sectors of the country. He calculated the rating of livestock in the fields of food, economy, social, and investment.

Research methodology

In the coverage of the scientific article, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the scientific works of well-known scientists in the social, economic, and political fields, their content and essence are studied, representing the development of this sector and the experience of advanced foreign countries in this. available indicators were statistically analyzed. Also, logical thinking, scientific observation, systematic approach, statistical and comparative analysis, traditional research methods, i.e. observation, comparison methods, were used in the study of statistical data and theories related to the topic. Scientific and technical information sources, textbooks, training manuals, foreign literature, periodical press, collections of scientific-practical conferences and Internet information were used to cover the topic. In addition, as of January 1, 2024, the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on livestock products produced and grown in all categories of farms using zootechnical and analytical methods, as well as the production of these products from the regions of Navoi region was analyzed.

Analysis and site

Many promising projects aimed at the development of the livestock sector are being implemented in our country. It is no exaggeration to say that hundreds of livestock complexes have appeared. These projects are important because they provide our people with cheap, high-quality meat and other food products, and also increase the employment and income of the citizens living in the village. The directions of the program for the development of the livestock industry and its branches in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 will stimulate the innovations implemented in the livestock industry in the country and contribute to the development of this industry.

Figure 1. Program directions for the development of the livestock industry and its branches in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026³

It is known that livestock economy is studied according to the following groups and types:

- Cattle breeding - in the direction of meat and milk;
- Sheep breeding - meat, wool, leather;
- Goat breeding - in the direction of wool and wool, milk;
- Poultry - in the direction of eggs and meat;
- Horse breeding - meat and milk, working animals and sports;
- Camel breeding - for meat, wool and milk;
- On cocooning;
- On beekeeping;
- On rabbit breeding;
- on the fisherman and others.

The total volume of livestock products grown in January-December 2023 was 201,969.5 billion soms. This indicator has increased by 3.7% compared to the corresponding period of 2022. The share of livestock products in the total volume of agricultural products was 49.9%. The consistent implementation of measures to increase the internal capabilities of the livestock sector, as well as the systematic support provided by the state, made it possible to increase the number of livestock and fill the domestic consumer markets with livestock products.

№	Product type	Unit of measure	2021	2022	2023
1	Cattle and poultry raised for	thousand tons	2 635,1	2 725,9	2 833,3

³ <https://lex.uz/docs/-5858728>

	slaughter - (in live weight).				
	including: x	thousand tons	x	x	x
1.1	large horned cattle	thousand tons	1 987,5	2 025,7	x
1.2	sheep and goats	thousand tons	409,6	418,0	x
1.3	pigs	thousand tons	3,2	2,9	x
1.4	poultry	thousand tons	220,7	265,7	x
1.5	other types of goods (horses, camels, rabbits, etc.)	thousand tons	14,1	13,6	x
2	Milk	thousand tons	11 274,2	11 627,2	11 968,7
2.1	of which, cow's milk	thousand tons	11 242,7	11 599,1	x
3	Obtained eggs	a total of mln. piece	7 788,4	8 129,2	8 487,5
3.1	from that, chicken eggs	mln. piece	7 749,4	8 089,2	x
4	Honey	Tons of honey	14 066,9	14 700,4	15 620,6
5	Sheared wool	Tons of sheared wool	36 345	37 307	38 639
6	Black skins were obtained	A thousand pieces	1 252,4	1 287,6	1 321,1
7	Cocoons	Tons of cocoons	22 769,9	24 300,2	25 885,8

Table 1 Production of livestock products in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2021-2023)⁴

The total live weight of cattle and poultry raised for slaughter was 2 million 833 thousand tons. Also, the production of 11.9 million tons of milk, 8.4 billion eggs, 1.3 million pelts, 38.6 thousand tons of wool, 25.9 thousand tons of cocoons and 15.6 thousand tons of honey was achieved. Meat (live weight) - 76.9 kg, milk - 323.3 kg, eggs - 228.2 per capita. Meat production increased by 3.9%, and the largest share in total agricultural products was 30.3%. In meat production, the share of Samarkand-11.5%, Kashkadarya-11.5%, Tashkent-10.8%, Bukhara-

⁴ <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/agriculture-2>

10.5% and regions was the highest. Milk production increased by 2.9% and made a 14.9% higher share in total agricultural products. 11.1 million tons of milk (93.2 percent) were produced by peasant (personal assistant) farms.

Figure 2. Meat (live weight), tons (2019-2023) ⁵

Compared to the last 4 years, the amount of meat in live weight has shown a significant increase. That is, 2023 will be 2,833.3 thousand tons, and this figure has increased by 107,300 tons compared to 2022. In 2019, we can see a difference of 359.7 thousand tons compared to 2023, with 2,473,600 tons of live weight meat. In the process of scientific research, the districts of Navoi region were analyzed by regions in the production of livestock products and the following indicators report was obtained. Live weight by all categories of farms in January-December 2023 188.3 thousand tons of meat (3.7% more than in January-December 2022) were produced. When the meat production indicators are analyzed by farm categories, it should be noted that 84.0 percent of the total volume of meat production was contributed by farmers and homestead farms.

Cow's milk, which is considered to be an important product of livestock farming, is mainly used in the country. About 95% of the milk consumed by the population is cow's milk, and it is mainly this type of milk that is discussed. In recent years, attention has been paid to the production of a new range of milk and milk products. For this purpose, practical works aimed at reconstruction of dairy production enterprises, enriching them with new, improved techniques and technologies are being carried out. The development of milk and milk products production technology is being implemented by using new physical methods.

⁵ Agriculture in Uzbekistan Facts and trends 2023

Figure 3. Milk extracted, thousand tons (2019-2023)⁶

Milk production increased by 2.9% and made a 14.9% higher share in total agricultural products. 11.1 million tons of milk (93.2 percent) were produced by peasant (personal assistant) farms. Milk produced in 2023 was 11,968 thousand tons, and we can see that the amount of milk has increased in the last 4 years. In 2022, this indicator included 11,629,000 tons, which is 300,000 tons less than this year. 539.3 thousand tons of milk (3.5% more compared to January-December 2022) were produced by farms of all categories in Navoi region, which accounts for 5 percent of the milk produced at the republic level, in January-December 2023.

Conclusions and suggestions.

It is known that the state's policy and consistent innovations, laws and regulatory documents on improving the livestock system, which is considered one of the indispensable branches of agriculture, which occupy an important place in the country's economy, encourage the competitiveness of the sector. Based on the fact that ensuring the well-being of the population is a priority, filling the consumer basket with another product is considered a positive situation for everyone. Based on the above, it is worth mentioning that the following suggestions should be made for further improvement of the industry.

Establishing modern methods of production of livestock products on the scale of the republic. It is natural that using these methods in the development of science and technology, the production of products from livestock with a high quality and consumption rate will contribute not only to the benefit of the people, but also to the export sector.

Implementation of digital technologies in the production of livestock products. Start a step-by-step transition to an automated system in the entire agricultural network. This convenience not only improves human health and work productivity, but also has an impact on productivity indicators in the country. Implementation of automated technologies on farms, milking machines for milking cows, equipment that cleans livestock waste and divides it into three stages.

Introduction of a single "PLATFORM" on the country level in order to increase the consumption of meat, milk and other livestock products. On this platform, based on the needs of the population, they can choose the types of products (choose milk with a fat content of 1.2.3.4 percent), or make a choice based on which part of the meat they eat (beef, thigh, loin, rib) "a,

⁶ Agriculture in Uzbekistan Facts and trends 2023

buttock"), the introduction of ways to make online purchases, the introduction of delivery services, taking into account the places of residence of the population, will not only save time, but also prevent various transport costs.

Improving the qualifications of personnel in the veterinary field, taking into account the fact that air pollution has a negative effect on the livestock industry. Relying on the experience of foreign countries, studying measures to prepare personnel for specialization and not to endanger the health of livestock.

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